

The Semio-Semantic and Social Study of the Media Role in Relation with COVID-19 in Pakistan: A Scientific, Social and Spiritual Analysis

(PhD English Linguistics Thesis)

Author Details: Robina Shaukat

Student ID: L4ENO13R16-009

Supervisor: Dr.Muhammad Shahbaz Arif

Department Of English Faculty Of Social Sciences And Humanities
Imperial College Of Business Studies,LCBS Lahore

Abstract

The study highlights the problems in present time media about issues in corona virus posts, videos, discussions safety measures about Covid19 in Pakistan on social media resources all that we are feeling, observing and watching of ourselves or about others, The researchers used the quantitative and qualitative research method and descriptive in nature. The researchers have started with collecting data from different websites and questionnaires and interviews discussions with learners and doctors for guidance and doctors for the semio-semantic analysis. The researchers have explored the social, economic, biological, psychological, moral, spiritual and demographic characteristics of the respondent, by investigating various social and economic dimensions that lead to the nature of problems of psychological issues as in abnormalities of perception, illusions of hallucinations as false conception, delusion as misperception, and schizophrenia. It is recommended that the quarantine 'LOCKDOWN' 2020 is not a horror but is an opportunity to turn back to family, friends and Allah Almighty's obligations. It's the best time to ponder upon what has been done in the past, amend the present and plan for a better future. It is recommended that on social media the use of sophisticated, and polished language free from religious, sectionalism and regional biased approach may be used. Humanity respect may be entertained and is appreciated in caring and healthy suggestions.

Key words: social media, modern era issues of bad health, wealth, materialistic approach , spiritual morality, life worth, save humanity.

CHAPTER 1**INTRODUCTION****1.1 Background**

According to Health Pakista National Institute a patient with severe fever and respiratory disease, cough, shortness of breath reported of Covid-19 .

1.1 Introduction

According to George Yule, Semiotics, or semiology, is the Semantics that is the study of the meaning of words and sentences are understood by mental representations of the speakers.

Corona19 started from China then moved to Italy., france America, England and entered in Pakistan in January, 2020. It has impacts of all spheres of life as economic, literal, psychological, religious activities, celebrations business approach ,job atmosphere and academic approach specially social media in genera's depiction as News ,YouTube, twitter, Facebook, what Sapp, personal accounts and so on.

Common prevention tips are as : to help stop the spread of COVID-19, tolisten for instructions from your local government about staying at home. manage to Keep a safe distance from others,to clean hands often and disinfect frequently touched surfaces at home.not to touch your eyes, nose or mouth and to Cover coughs and sneezes with your elbow or tissue. Staying at home saves lives. Everyone can get help by the source that are measured for protection.

To share true picture of complexity in their approaches to sociolinguistics, ethnography, gender and language variations, economical aspects, religious identifications, interaction, contextualized approaches, personality challenges, threats, conversational analysis, discursive psychological Feminist Post-structuralism Discourse Analysis, Coverd dressed, coverd language wrapped in moral sophisticated level had been target throughout the world by developed set up to marginalize and suppress the spiritual minded people specially female as hindrance to progress and development .

According to behavioral sciences study, to Marriam (2020), this movie depicts the secret horror of everyone who is in quarantine in covid 2020, especially the ones who live alone. Being is a social animal, a human can't live without interaction with others, in this video, a young boy is also killing his time by talking to his girlfriend so that the time may pass peacefully. This is a general basic requirement and to some extent weakness of a human being, that he can't live alone. He needs anyone who listens to him, talks to him, spends a value time with him.Secondly, the horror film is visualizing the mind of a person who is locked down in his house. And due to his loneliness, he is facing many psychological problems like depression, anxiety, insomnia. To overcome his depression and to enhance his mental activity, he is smoking as well. Due to insomnia he can't sleep even at 2:30am. These are some side effects experienced by a person who has no social companion to live with. Thirdly, due to a very long duration of staying home alone, he might have developed some sort of schizophrenia or delusion or even hallucination. In this video, the boy might have visual and auditory hallucination. That's why, he is feeling that someone else is also at home and will definitely kill him.

1.3 Research Questions

Following are questions as,

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the social and spiritual characteristics of the social media users?
2. How can the various social and economic dimensions can be measured?
3. What are the methods to determine the psychological impacts of media?
4. Which are measures to address growing problems of modern era?
5. How can the semio-semantic and economic dimensions be measured?

1.4 Thesis Statement

About covid 19 disease, symptoms, care and solution of medicine of vaccine, proper care, use of kit of gloves, shoes, head cover cap, the semio-semantic and social study of the media role in psychological approach and spiritual remedy for the peace of heart and conscious.

1.5 Key Terms

In key terms of confirmed case of corona virus affected one. In term of Contact a contact is a person , dress, gloves , goggles, shoe covers or by other situations as indicated by local risk assessments. It is of great importance that for confirmed asymptomatic cases,

1.6 Significance of the Study

Standardize medicine to conduct research on applied nutrition.

1.7 Rationale (Objectives)

In order to explore the reasons how did Corona virus-19 Spread , treatment and Prevention, to investigate the various social and economic dimensions that lead to media role, to study the nature of media problems, to determine the impacts of media on the mind of people and to find out the media role in addressing the mass audience. The major reasons how did Corona virus-19 Spread, treatment and Prevention, to investigate the various social and economic dimensions that lead to media role, to study the nature of media problems, to determine the impacts of media on the mind of people and to find out the media role in addressing the mass audience. Reasons how did Corona virus-19 spread, investigate the various social and economic dimensions that lead to horror of lockdown 2020 and its impacts on the mind of people and find out the semio-semantic study of the short horror film "lockdown,2020, addressing the mass audience.

1.8 Division of Chapter

In division of chapter are background of topic as background, Introduction, Research Question, Thesis Statement, Key Terms, Significance Rationale discussed.

Fig No.1 Modal

(According to Broderick's Maria Dissertation (2002).

CHAPTER.2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Reports by World's Health Organization (WHO)

According to WHO about Novel Coronavirus (2019-nCoV) in situation report – 1, posted on 21 January 2020. It is submitted the Summary as event highlights from 31 December 2019 to 20 January 2020, On 31 December 2019, the WHO China Country Office was informed of cases of pneumonia, unknown etiology (unknown cause) detected, Hubei of China. On 3 January 2020, a total of 44 case-patients with pneumonia of unknown etiology were reported to WHO by the national authorities in China. During this reported period, the causal agent was not identified. On 11 and 12 January 2020, WHO received further detailed information from the National Health Commission China that the outbreak is associated with exposures in one seafood market in Wuhan City. The Chinese authorities identified a new type of coronavirus, which was isolated on 7 January 2020. On 12 January 2020, China shared the genetic sequence of the novel coronavirus for countries to use in developing specific diagnostic kits. On 13 January 2020, the Ministry of Public Health, Thailand reported the first imported case of lab-confirmed novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) from Wuhan, Hubei Province, China. On 15 January 2020, the Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare, Japan (MHLW) reported an imported case of laboratory-confirmed 2019-novel coronavirus (2019-nCoV) from Wuhan, Hubei Province, China. On 20 January 2020, National IHR Focal Point (NFP) for Republic of Korea reported the first case of novel coronavirus in the Republic of Korea.

2.2 Reported incidence of confirmed 2019-nCoV cases

Table 1. Countries, territories or areas with reported confirmed cases of 2019-nCoV, 20 January 2020 WHO Regional Office.

China – Hubei Province	258
China – Guangdong	14
China – Beijing Municipality	05
China – Shanghai Municipality	01
Japan	01
Republic of Korea	01
SEARO Thailand	02
Total confirmed cases	282

WHO has been in regular and direct contact with Chinese as well as Japanese, Korean and Thai authorities since the reporting of these cases. The three countries have shared information with WHO under the International Health Regulations. WHO is also informing other countries about the situation and providing support as requested. On 2 January, the incident management system was activated across the three levels of WHO (country office, regional office and headquarters); Developed the surveillance case definitions for human infection with 2019-nCoV and is updating it as per the new information becomes available; Developed interim guidance for laboratory diagnosis, clinical management, infection prevention and control in health care settings, home care for mild patients, risk communication and community engagement; Prepared disease commodity package for supplies necessary in identification and management of confirmed patients; Provided recommendations to reduce risk of transmission from animals to humans; Updated the travel advice or international travel in health in relation to the outbreak of pneumonia caused by a new coronavirus in China; Utilizing global expert networks and partnerships for laboratory, infection prevention and control, clinical management and mathematical modeling. Activation of R&D blueprint to accelerate diagnostics, vaccines, ad

therapeutics; WHO is working with our networks of researchers and other experts to coordinate global work on surveillance, epidemiology, modeling, diagnostics, clinical care and treatment, and other ways to identify, manage the disease and limit onward transmission. WHO has issued interim guidance for countries, updated to take into account the current situation.

2.5 Manpower response to covid 19

In country response by China, Thailand, Japan and Republic of Korea were managed. National authorities were conducting active case finding in all provinces; Since 14 January 2020, 35 infrared thermometers had been installed in airports, railway stations, long-distance bus stations, and ferry terminals; Search expanded for additional cases within and outside of Wuhan City; Active / retroactive case finding in medical institutions in Wuhan City; The Hunan Seafood Wholesale Market in Wuhan city was closed on 1 January 2020 for environmental sanitation and disinfection. Market inspection in expansion to other markets; Public education on disease prevention and environmental hygiene further strengthened in public places across the city, farmers' markets in particular.

2.3 Symptoms of coronavirus

According to Drs Yao and Wang (2020), In January 2020, corona virus entered in family in China with symptoms of fever, sore throat and respiratory symptom. Its estimated that the coronavirus may have been transmitted by touching and asymptomatic carrier. Till 26th of January two more patients have the same symptoms. Same symptoms were found in Italy, Iran and then in Pakistan with the border crossing of Pilgrims from Iran in Qumtana center in March, 2020. By M. Khan -March 30, 2020, according to Pakistan Institute of Development Economics, The effected people in Pakistan rose to 1,670 till mid of March, 2020. Punjab were 45 more patients, taking to 638 from 593 from the previous day. Earlier, the national dashboard had reported with six new cases in Sindh; three in KPK; five in Gilgit Baltistan and eight new cases of Islamabad. The country also reported two new deaths, taking the nation-wide 19. Welfare Dr Azra Pechuho confirmed the death of two more patients in the country. "Both 52 and 66-year-old patients and had been confirmed with Covid-19 three days earlier. The health minister said in a statement. Punjab recorded the highest number of coronavirus cases in the country, 638, with Sindh coming in second with 508. KP has reported 195 cases, Balochistan 144, Islamabad 51, Gilgit- Baltistan 128 and AJK six.

2.4 Sensations of horror in lockdown

According to Creed the horror film may be dealt as an illustration. It is found that a horror film satisfies a wish to save pleasure. It is explained by Creed that in Kristeva's view, the feminine body is most specifically polluting mind and soul. The excremental is more closely related to the mother's semiotic mapping of the infant's body, as it is unable to clean up its own abjections and relies on a maternal figure. Kristeva's use of the term "semiotic," a term which most would associate with post-structuralist theory, to describe signs and symbols and their use or interpretation for Kristeva refers to the language, action, sound and music.

Dr Indu Rao (2020), described that Lockdown is a blessing in disguise for learners, parents, doctors for guidance, business men and all. It was added that for learning purposes, there are plenty of study courses and material in nature around. It was further guided that in LOCKDOWN 2020, there is a technique, active participation, cleanliness measures, cleanliness of mind, body and soul rather than horror. Horror had been the characteristic of dirty, polluted, frustrated mind, heart and soul. Dr Indu Rao further guided that In the hectic schedules of current modern computerized educational system, learners had no leisure time. In Lockdown 2020, learners can also pursue their passion for reading, writing, music and other extra-curricular options. Learners should not think they

have been left behind or harmed by this lockdown. Instead, such learners have got more time to spend with their parents, to witness and reflect on the true nature, meaning and purpose of life, to develop a higher empathy towards humanity and to set their priorities right. The current lockdown is a blessing in disguise.

2.6 Covid 19 in Pakistan

According to D's Yao and Wang (2020), In January 2020, corona virus entered in family in China with symptoms of fever, sore throat and respiratory symptom. Its estimated that the coronavirus may have been transmitted by touching and asymptomatic carrier. Till 26th of January two more patients have the same symptoms. Same symptoms were found in Italy, Iran and then in Pakistan with the border crossing of Pilgrims from Iran in Qurentena center in March, 2020. By M. Khan -March 30, 2020, according to Pakistan Institute of Development Economics, The number of confirmed coronavirus cases in Pakistan rose to 1,670 till mid of March, 2020. Punjab reported 45 new cases, taking the provincial tally to 638 from 593 from the previous day. Earlier, the national dashboard had reported with six new cases in Sindh; three in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa; three in Baluchistan; five in Gilgit Baltistan and eight new cases in Islamabad. The country also reported two new deaths, taking the nation-wide toll to 19. Sindh's Minister for Health and Population Welfare Dr Azra Pechuho confirmed the death of two more patients in the country. "Both 52 and 66-year-old patients were residents of Karachi and had been diagnosed with COVID-19 three days back. The 66-year-old patient had renal issues and was on dialysis regularly and the 52-year-old patient had a respiratory problem," the health minister said in a statement. Punjab has recorded the highest number of coronavirus cases in the country, 638, with Sindh coming in second with 508. KP has reported 195 cases, Baluchistan 144, Islamabad 51, Gilgit-Baltistan 128 and AJK six. Reported illnesses have ranged from mild symptoms to severe illness and death for confirmed coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) cases' According to oronavirus update as of Friday confirmed cases rise to 2,458 in Pakistan. In Sindh: 783, in Punjab: 928, in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa: 311, in Baluchistan: 169, in Islamabad: 62, in Gilgit-Baltistan: 187, in Azad Kashmir: 09, Deaths: 37 while Globally over 52,000 people have so far died of the deadly disease.

Fig No.24 Modal (Broderick's Maria Dissertation (2002).

CHAPTER 3

METHODOLOGY

METHODOLOGY

The present research is fundamental analytic research method and qualitative by net websites as near-2300- -surpasses30. The researchers have got login access to Academia website. Data were collected by online google form doc questionnaires to find out the social and spiritual impact of social media.

3.1 Sample

Doctors for guidance from Pakistan, learners and numbers of teacher's respondents.

	Doctors as guide	learners
Doctors for guidance discussions	19	
Discussions about learners young generation		129
Problems and solutions	Fifteen	

Table 2: Sample

3.2 Population

The doctors for guidance and learners of Pakistan

3.3 Respondents

Doctors for guidance ,129 learners 15 doctors for guidance for awareness.

3.4 Data Collection

By doctors for guidance and learners and web sites.

3.5 Procedure

In google form doc. online classes and information data were collected about the purpose of study then its results were analysed by SPSS.

3.6 Tools

For data collection .questionnaires, discussions were tools

3.7 Data Analysis

In order to analyse data, SPSS software was used to get graphs in pie and bar shapes.

Summary

To get data parts in methodology section are data from sampling, , learners and doctors for guidance.

Fig No.25 Picture of Modal

(As Broderick's Maria 2002)

Chapter4

Results & Finding

Section 1 Results (A)

Table.3

(A) Doctors for guidance

No	Description	Strongly Disagree	Dis agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Culture is depicted through media	-	-	14	5
2	during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home	6	5	7	1
3	it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos	-	-	6	13
4	Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal	1	-	10	8
5	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator	-	-	4	15
6	Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.	2	2	13	2
7	COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.	-	-	9	10
8	human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations	5	4	9	1
9	Women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon	3	2	7	7
10	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology	3	-	8	8

Table.4

Doctors for guidance views (N=19)

Table.4 Doctors for guidance %

		% Disagree	% Strongly disagree	% Agree	% Strongly Agree
1	Culture is depicted through media	-	-	74%	26%
2	during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home	32%	26%	37%	05%
3	it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos	-	-	32%	68%
4	Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal	05%	-	53%	42%
5	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator	-	-	21%	79%
6	Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.	11%	11%	67%	11%
7	COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.	-	-	47%	53%
8	human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations	26%	22%	47%	05%
9	Women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon	15%	11%	37%	37%
10	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology	16%	-	42%	42%

In response 1, about identification of the role of media in culture 76% weightage show that selection and identification is very important. In response 2, 37 % raito strongly agree shows culture is depicted through media. In response 3, it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube videos the statement is supported by 68% respondents. In response 4, about Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat,

continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal is supported by 53% respondents. In response 5, about Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator is 79 % supported by respondents. In response 6, about Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures ,and 67 % respondents supported the statement. In response 7, about COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, busine washing hands, sses, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic is supported by 53% respondents. In response 8, about human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations". The statement is supported by 47% respondents. In response 9, about economic empowerment strategies are to Develop women's career , is supported by 37% respondents. In response 10, about isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology is supported by 42% respondents.

Results (B)

Table.5

129 Learners

		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Culture is depicted through media	4	6	68	51
2	during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home	62	33	17	17
3	it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos	2	5	43	79
4	Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal	15	9	63	42
5	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator	1	9	60	59
6	Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.	13	7	90	19
7	COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.	7	7	38	77
8	human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations	42	35	34	18

9	Women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon	26	27	43	33
10	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology	5	10	48	66

It was found that mostly (68) learners had strongly agreed that identification of the role of media in culture is very important during lockdown is strongly disagreed by 62 learners. It's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube videos during lockdown in covid 19 is strongly agreed by 79 learners. Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect and rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal, is agreed by 63 learners. Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator is agreed by 60 learners. Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures agreed by 90 learners. COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic strongly agreed by 77 learners. "human rights are of great importance during lockdown situation" is agreed by 34 learners. economic empowerment strategies are to develop women's career , women can help as integral part to balance economic disaster during lockdown is agreed by 43 learners. Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology is strongly agreed by 66 learners.

19 Teachers %

Sr No	Statement	Disagree(%)	Strongly disagree(%)	Agree(%)	Strongly Agree(%)
1	Culture is depicted through media	-	-	74%	26%
2	during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home	32%	26%	37%	05%
3	it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos	-	-	32%	68%
4	Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal	05%	-	53%	42%
5	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator	-	-	21%	79%
6	Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.	11%	11%	67%	11%
7	COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in	-	-	47%	53%

	particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.				
8	human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations	26%	22%	47%	05%
9	women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdown	15%	11%	37%	37%
10	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology	16%	-	42%	42%

Culture is depicted through media. is agreed by 53 % respondents. Its pleasant to stay time with family members at home aimlessly during lockdown is disagreed by 48% respondents. It's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube videos strongly agreed by 61% respondents. Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal is agreed by 49% respondents. Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator is agreed by 46% respondents. Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures is agreed by 70 % respondents. COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic is strongly agreed by 60 % respondents, "human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations".

Section : 1 Results (C)Open ended

How media website selection is to be careful in psychological impacts on behaviors towards the COVID-19 by managing selection of authentic websites?

Question 2 shows that 6 doctors for guidance , 50% were agreed that the purposes of Behavior-change interventions to improve during COVID19 situations is very valuable aspects to improve spiritual and moral psychological approach to save humanity peace of mind during lockdown and its aftereffects.

Question 3 indicates that out of 15, 50% doctors for guidance are in favor of to get through the impact of Coronavirus on Economy by managing small level business, online teaching, online jobs etc.

Question 4 We should improve the situation of psychological restlessness and mental anxiety in covid effects situations is agreed by 50% of doctors for guidance . covid 19 is helpful in new revival of human mind, soul, psyche, behavior, atmosphere and surroundings ?

Question 5 Covid 19 is helpful in new revival of human mind, soul, psyche, behavior, atmosphere and surroundings as people have got a chance to ponder about past mistakes, revival in present time and the best latest revised planning for future.

SECTION 2

FINDINGS

The semio-semantic and social study of the Media Role in Relation with Covid -19 in Pakistan about it is found that nothing is good or bad but its use, selection and time makes it so. As media is not bad its selection makes its good effective or bad and dangerous.

4.1 Findings (A) (19 Doctors for guidance)

doctors for guidance and respondent's web sites showed these findings.

Statement 1("Culture is depicted through media." 14/19)

Statement 2 (".during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home " dis agreed 06/19)

Statement 3 ("It's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube videos .:13/19)

Statements 4 ("Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal.rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal. "10/19).

Statement 5 Strong trends were observed ("Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator."15 /19)

Statement 6 too showed strong trends (Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures."13/19).

Statement 7 ("COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic."10/19)

Statement 8 ("human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations"9/19).

Statement 9 ("economic empowerment strategies are to Develop women's career , .:7/19).

Statement 10 ("Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology ." 8/19)

4.1.1FigNo1 Culture is depicted through media."

About question 1, "Culture is depicted through media." data collected in which 14 doctors for guidance were agreed Culture is depicted through media.

Fig 1 :(b) "Culture is depicted through media." %

"Culture is depicted through media" while 74% doctors for guidance were agreed that Culture is depicted through media.

Fig No. 2(a) during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home

Six learners were strongly disagreed that its pleasant to stay time with family members at home.

Fig No. 2(b). during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home %

From above pie graph results it was clear that 37% doctors for guidance were infavour that during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home

Fig No. 3 it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube videos

None of the respondents was against the views that while 13 doctors for guidance strongly agreed that it's good time pass and source of recreation and knowledge gate such as YouTube videos.

Fig No. 3 (b) it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos %

It showed that 68% doctors for guidance were agreed that it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube videos.

Fig 4(a): Corona symtoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal.

Fig 4(a) 10 doctors for guidance were in favour of the fact that Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal

Fig 4(b) Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal.

From above fig 4(b) it could be Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal. Inferred that. Mostly, 53% doctors for guidance were in favor that

Fig No.5 Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator

Fig 5(a) showed that Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator

Fig 5 (b) Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator. %

Fig 5(b) represented not a single respondent was in favour of isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator.

Fig No. 6 Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.

Fig 6(a) It was clearly shown that 13 doctors for guidance were in favor of the Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.

Fig 6(b) Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures. %

The results of pie graph showed that 11% doctors for guidance did not accept the ways to prevent the disease as only by washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.

Fig No.7 COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.

10 doctors for guidance were strongly agreed that COVID-19’s impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.

Fig 7(b) COVID-19’s impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic. %

It was clear that COVID-19’s impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.

Doctors for guidance 53% were strongly agreed about COVID-19’s impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.

Fig No.8 “human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations”.

This pie graph results showed that doctors for guidance 9/19 had showed positive response about respect and honor for human rights during lockdown situations.

Fig 8(b) “human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations” %

The above charts indicated that human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations

Fig No.9 economic empowerment strategies are to Develop women’s career, women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon

7/19 doctors for guidance were agreed that “economic empowerment strategies are to Develop women’s career , women can help as integral part to balance economical disaster during lockdown”

Fig 9(b) : economic empowerment strategies are to Develop women’s career , women can help as integral part to balance economical disaster during lockdown

. %

It was depicted from above fig that only 11% doctors for guidance were not infavour of economic empowerment strategies to Develop women’s career , women can help as integral part to balance economical disaster during lockdown as well.

Fig No. Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology.

In response to the question regarding social distance in coronavirus is biologically good but damage the psychology, 8 doctors for guidance had strongly agreed that coronavirus effects damage the psychology.

Fig 10(b): Social distance in coronavirus is biologically good but damages the psychology. %

From the above it was depicted that doctors for guidance positively admitted that isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology

4.2 Section. (B) : Findings (Data Collection by 129 Learners)

Section 2nd dealt with linguistic questions to collect data by 129 learners. with the help of questionnaires

Statement 1 was strongly agreed by learners (“Identification of the role of media in culture is very important”68/129).

Statement 2 was strongly disagreed by learners, (“Its pleasant to stay time with family members at home.”62/129).

Statement 3 was admitted positively (“it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos”79/129).

Statement 4 was admitted (“Corona symptoms of Hot Fever, Sore Throat, Coughing and Shortness Of Breath rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal. ”63/129).

Statement 5 was agreed, (“Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator”60/129).

Statement 6 was mostly agreed, (“Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.”90/129).

Statement 7 was strongly appreciated (“COVID-19’s impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic. ”77/129).

Statement 8 was critically strongly disagreed (“human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations”42/129).

Statement 9 was also strongly liked (“women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon”43/129).

Statement 10 was very strongly appreciated (“Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology .”66/129).

Fig No 11. (a Culture is depicted through media).

It was clear that 129, 51/129 learners had strongly in favor of the statement that Culture is depicted through media

Fig 11(b): Culture is depicted through media.%

Fig 11. (b)

From above graph it was clear that 53% learners were agreed that Culture is depicted through media

Fig No.12 (a) during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home.

Fig 12(a). Its pleasant to stay time with family members at home.

62 learners strongly disagreed that during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home

Fig 12(b). during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home %

From above fig it could be inferred that during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home.

Fig No.13 (a) it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos

About it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos , 79129 learners were positive.

Fig 13(b) it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos %

The above bar graph clearly depicted that that (61%) learners were positive about that it was better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos

Fig No. 14 (a) Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal.

Out of 129, 63 learners agreed with that Corona symptoms of Hot Fever, Sore Throat, Coughing and Shortness Of Breath rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal, . So, learners were in favor of Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal,

Fig 14(b) Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal,%

The above chart showed that Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal rebuilt the faith with spiritual aspect that life is mortal,

Fig No. 15 (a) Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator.

Above picture showed that 60/129 learners, were positive about the fact that the Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator

Fig 15 (b) Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator %

The above chart also indicated that Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator

Fig No. 16 Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.

The above picture depicted that mostly 90/129 learners were agreed that Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.

Fig 16 (b) Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.%

the learners were positive with ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.

Fig No. 17: COVID-19’s impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.

It was clear that COVID-19’s impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.77 learners had strongly agreed with this point.

Fig No.17 (b) COVID-19’s impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.%

The above figure revealed that COVID-19’s impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.

Fig No. 18 “human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations”.

Learners were in positive approach about the fact that “human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations” 42 learners had disagreed with this fact.

Fig No 18(b). “human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations”%

It is observed from the above chart that “human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations”

Fig No.19 Economic empowerment strategies are to Develop women’s career women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon

Mostl learners were positive about the statement that economic empowerment strategies are to Develop women’s career , women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon , then 43 learners had agreed with this point.

Fig No 19 (b) Economic empowerment strategies are to Develop women’s career , women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon %

It was observed from the above chart that economic empowerment strategies are to Develop women’s career , women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon. Mostly learners as (33%) were of the positive opinion.

Fig No. 20 Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology.

Mostly respondents were in favor of the statement that the Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology, 66 learners had strongly agreed with the effectiveness of the statement.

Fig No. 20(b) Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology %

The above figure also indicated that mostly respondents were in positive approach about the statement that about isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology,

4.3 Section. (C) : Findings (Data Collection by 15 Doctors for guidance with 5 open ended)

Section (C) dealt with 5 open ended linguistic questions to collect data by 15 English language doctors for guidance . Finding and results were extracted by software SPSS,

1. How can you manage Impact of mass media and social media on psychological attitudes and behaviors towards the COVID-19 ?

It was observed that mass media had left impacts upon psychological attitudes and behaviors towards the COVID-19. People had become conscious to remain clean and clear in their cleanliness if hands, eyes, ears, throat, hair and physical hygiene. They had revised their home setting, planned to cut short unnecessary relation and improved business dealings,

2. What are the purposes of Behavior-change interventions to improve during COVID19 situations ?

Doctors for guidance liked improvement in behavior as useful, reliable member of home domain, society and loyal to themselves. It was observed as ample time to think about past mistakes, improvement in present and best planning for coming future.

3. How Can to get Through The Impact of Coronavirus on Pakistan Economy ?

Personal approach, struggle and will power was observed by doctors for guidance . Some doctors for guidance had argued about very wide range to improve business by online approach. During smart lockdown.

4. How should we improve the situation of psychological restlessness and mental anxiety in covid effects situations ?

Doctors for guidance psychological restlessness and mental anxiety in covid effects situations as revision of budget. Cleanliness and managing home appliances, paying more attention to improve morality, sincerity and integrity and peace of contentment.

5. How covid 19 is helpful in new revival of human mind, soul, psyche, behavior, atmosphere and surroundings ?

Doctors for guidance in new revival of human mind, soul, psyche, behavior, atmosphere and surroundings. Smart lockdown had been discussed as a golden chance to avail time of life of vigor again. It had been observed opportunity about freshness in atmosphere and free world from water ,air and environmental pollution, having friendly.

Fig No. 22 Question 1 How can you manage Impact of mass media and social media on psychological attitudes and behaviors towards the COVID-19 ?

Fig 22 question 1 shows that 6 doctors for guidance , 50% were agreed that Impact of mass media and social media on psychological attitudes and behaviors towards the COVID-19 can be managed by best selection of media broadcast material.

Fig No. 23 Question 2 What are the purposes of Behavior-change interventions to improve during COVID19 situations ?

This picture shows that out of 15, 50% doctors for guidance are in favor of the purposes of Behavior-change interventions to improve during COVID19 situations and are fully aware of its purpose through media role.

Fig No. 24 Question 3 How Can to get Through The Impact of Coronavirus on Pakistan Economy? Small businesses are particularly vulnerable

This Picture shows that the Impact of Coronavirus on Pakistan Economy can be managed by Small businesses are particularly vulnerable while they were totally ignored and neglected.

Fig No. 25 Question 4 How should we improve the situation of psychological restlessness and mental anxiety in covid effects situations ?

The pie graph results clearly shows that 50% doctors for guidance to improve psychological restlessness and mental anxiety in covid effects situations.

Fig No. 26 Question 5 How covid 19 is helpful in new revival of human mind, soul, psyche, behavior, atmosphere and surroundings

It is clear by above picture that 50% doctors for guidance covid 19 is helpful in new revival of human mind, soul, psyche, behavior, atmosphere and surroundings of media awareness.

Summary

Doctors for guidance are satisfied with about with use of latest media approaches learning and gaining at home during smart lockdown. It was observed that in fighting disease the importance of health and life liberty is judged properly.

Fig No.26 Results & Findings.
(Modal Maria Broderick2002).

CHAPTER 5**CONCLUSION****5.1 Finding's summary**

The researchers have explored the social and demographic characteristics of the, investigate the various websites of social media and its disastrous nature of problems of media users impacts of language use on the mind of people, the role of media in addressing the mass audience and propose measures to address growing problems of coronavirus, its social and spiritual characteristics to investigating personality ideas, utilized individual personalities attributes, people embrace etymological or articulations that list starting point, sex, age, or class distinction, social, religious, spiritual and sectional aspect show social groupings.

The researchers have explored in this short film, a young boy is smoking, talking to his girlfriend. In short, he's sitting useless. He is unaware of the blessing that God has given him TIME to re-set his life but he is facing psychotic problems. He should sit for a while and think about his deeds and his repentance. This time is given for repentance. And Allah loves those who repent. This time is not a time of leisure, fun and useless activities. It is the time to rebirth. 'LOCKDOWN' 2020 is the greatest gift of nature as it never comes back. According to William Shakespeare (1612), it's up to man to make hell out of heaven and heaven out of hell. The short horror film depicts the social and demographic characteristics of the modern computer age man whose life is full of worries, restlessness and conscious disturbance. It is suggested that this quarantine is an opportunity to turn back to family, friends and Allah Almighty's obligations. Restlessness, materialistic approach and weak faith on creator Allah Almighty are the social and spiritual characteristics of the social media users. The various social and economic dimensions can be measured with application of fear of creator in mind and heart. The methods to determine the psychological impacts of media are to collect data and its analysis. Negligence towards rights and duties are measures to address growing problems of modern era. The various social and economic dimensions be measured in the concept of horror in the mind for the deeds to get hell or heaven at the end of the life journey. The effects of lockdown on the attitude of youth can be measured by their horror, fear, restlessness and dissatisfaction of mind and heart.

5.2 Conclusions

The researchers have explored the social and demographic characteristics of the, investigate the various websites of social media and its disastrous nature of problems of media users impacts of language use on the mind of people, the role of media in addressing the mass audience and propose measures to address growing problems of coronavirus, its social and spiritual characteristics to investigating personality ideas, utilized individual personalities attributes, people embrace etymological or articulations that list starting point, sex, age, or class distinction, social, religious, spiritual and sectional aspect show social groupings.

In political collocates, as far the word "political" is assessed and has been observed, as political parties, political participation, political activities, characterization of political personalities, political information, ways of political campaign about candidates, celebrations comments, pictures, statements, political exposure in political scenario, figures and features of political demonstration are discussed in details to find out the use of social media impact on society, scientific approach and human psychology. Lock down effects shows remarkable ratio. On social networks, its greater volume offers a great world level academic publications, incorporated advertising, dealing of infected patients in an innovative way, social network adds, availability of greater market in greater volume, offering a new model to advertise, advertising on one social network site. It is notable that social media is continually growing to get safety is health insurance, safety for public transportation, safety at home, safety in offices, safety to use electronics, safety from infections and safety by herbal and homeopathic medicare.

In order to find out the use of social media impact on society, scientific approach and human psychology. The psychological aspects of youth captives in homes with no fast food, no availability of drives, no servants, no cook, no cinemas, no outside fun, no outside visit and date with girlfriend, no liberty to move outside freely, no chance to show latest fashioned dresses, no chance to move in latest model car, no chance to wear latest brand shoes, no chance to show off latest fashion of haircut, no chance to have race in car. These are the victims of hallucination and feel insecure locked in their homes. The only character represents the youth of modern era facing restrictions and his dialogues with his girlfriend also represent nothingness growing inside. Indecisive talk with the ghost is the frustration of restlessness of lockdown which is killing the liberty of youth and so on. The scene of sitting aimlessly and the smoking to kill the time. The dead hour of time represented the restlessness of mind, heart and soul. Having feeling the shades of hands on the back showed restlessness, to feel the presence of monster on piano is frustrated sign of hallucination. His conscious is not clear. He feel burden of previous life deeds of no virtue. In feelings of horror, he did not want to take refuge in the lap of nature or creator rather again called to his girlfriend to cover the frustration. As cat closes her eyes to save herself from monster pigeon, the boy entered the bed and took the quilt over him. There was no monster in reality. It was his frustrated attitude and hallucination that he considered that, the monster had tried to kill him with dragon. The character can represent the frustrated attitude and hallucination of young generation.

In horror short film by a Pakistani artist, is the depiction of horror. According to Paul Acker cited Tolkien's essay "Beowulf: The Monster and The critics" have discussed that readers achieved intentions, that of placing the monsters at the center, rather than at the periphery. After the life corruption there is restlessness in heart and mind. It leads to hallucination and illusion of mind. Horror of next generation penalties, horror of failure in life, disrespect in the eyes of people, social status breakdown dilemma, economical collapse, dishonor in this mortal world and the immortal eternal spiritual world hereafter. The horror does not stand for a monster but the horror is in the heart and mind. If a person is satisfied on his actions, thoughts and dealings, he has no fear but faith on Allah Almighty, that is the first ladder of faith sovereignty to go for believe and confirmed eternal bliss.

According to Katherine Tillman (2012), the opening word lockdown stands for engaging with fictions stimulating the conscious thoughts. The spread of corona virus, its effects on life, its safety measures to wash hands with sanitizers, wearing masque on face, wearing gargles, wearing head cover, wearing gloves, wearing shoe covers, all have made the atmosphere in hospitals, in news pictures, in films, in documentary reports all give horror picture for kids, children young people, old ones and female specially.

The young boy in the horror film is universal character. He stands for all the people of all ages and all gender and age level. He stands for lonely young boy, a lover, a defeated person, a social being to miss the friends company, a jobless person worried about money, a business man thinking about lost business loss due to lock down, a husband not satisfied in the company of wife, a father who is not happy in the sweet company of kids, a brother who is not feeling blessed with sister, a brother who has missed and lost his real companionship in his real brother. In fact he is a live body without passion and soul. In the mind cells there is disturbance and to save the life, family company is needed.

It also indicate the thoughts of an old man who has spent all of his life in evil ways, marry making and neglecting the good deeds. He has sold his soul to devil and adopted sins, evil doings, extravagancy and lechery rather than piety. The setting of his room indicates that he is a person of materialistic approach. He has worldly aims instead of eternal bliss. The word LOCKDOWN stands for his fate is locked, his will, happiness, desire, merry making, bliss, satisfaction is finished and locked. On the other hand this boy stands for spiritual alarming and warning that we must repent before death and real lockdown of eternal death. The developed countries had been target the covered dress of women considering from lower class but now in virus spreading scenario the whole worlds men, women, kids, young and old are in gloves, masques, covered full dresses from head to toe. It indicated that covering the body is to save body, to save soul and to save life. It shows that life is precious and precious things are kept in covered custody.

In the film, time of night in solitude describes disturbance in mind. As John Edgar Browning cited David (1929) in Classical Hollywood Horror, that 1929, claimed horror film. It was a moment the dark shade waited for. Mental retardation is clear to kill time by smoking activity. Lockdown stand to refrain from social activities. It stands for to say good bye to enjoyment of social, economic and physical entertainment. On the other hand it leads to lockdown bad habits, bad customs, and bad activities, refrain from bad company. It stands for backbiting, time wastage in useless meetings. It indicates saving in dresses, cosmetics, utensils, shoes, useless accessories without whom life is in peace. Lockdown is good to control vehicles to free the world environment from air land and water pollution. Lockdown gives rich time to company family members and to probe into the family gossips that had been never done in hectic hours of busy routine life. Lockdown takes man close to love of nature, love of missing fellow beings and love of the humanity in a real sense.

West, L. J. (Ed.). (1962) discussed about hallucinations in the joint American Psychiatric Association. A symposium on hallucinations was held in December 1958. In this photograph of short horror film, neurophysiologic theory of hallucinations; the role of the brain stem reticular formation are discussed.

In this click of a short horror film, pharmacodynamics of hallucinations; comparison of drug induced and psychotic hallucinations are depicted by Daniel Carey to show that when conscious is not satisfied then every contact is lost. It interprets that when one loses his contact with Allah Almighty, the creator, then every signal is disconnected. Love of creator is the main current to activate all organs and open all keys of life.

In this picture of a short horror film, concept of hallucination in sleep deprivation, visual hallucinations; hallucinations in schizophrenia; hallucinations in young slot; effects of Covid-19 on our society foretold by Defoe long ago are discussed as there is end of every link and contact.

In this horror film the young boy stands for young generation of computer age, busy in screen time involvement rather than the green time in natural environment. The horror is not in film it is in the mind and heart of every person. This horror leads man to go for right path, right ways. If it is law of nature that ever poor, rich and mediocre has to taste death. Then all men will die as law of nature. In Sufism approach after this mortal life there is eternal life hereafter. All will get reward or punishment on the day of judgement.

In use of all genera, novel, film, or social media covid-19 has impacts on the social, physical, economical, spiritual impacts on mind and soul of the people. Deaths rate has generated horror among masses. After taking any step in business, there is ray of hope and horror. In taking any test or exam there is horror in mind. For the biggest test of man decision of hell and heaven has the peak level of horror in heart for those who did not spend the past in a good justified way. Lockdown is a chance to revise the deeds , actions and complete life.

The News Page on Monday April 27, 2020, in entertainment page, Selena Gomez enjoys TikTok video of dances on her song on Boyfriend dancing to her song 'Boyfriend'. Healthcare workers, who are executing their duties valiantly during coronavirus pandemic across the globe, try to relieve their stress by dancing and singing during the ongoing crisis. Selena has lauded the frontline warriors and shared a TikTok video of two nurses dancing to her latest song 'Boyfriend'. The nurses had shared their dance video on their personal social media handles after which the singer took notice and reposted the clip. The 'Rare' singer wrote: "This made me smile so much!! Thank you to every single medical professional on the frontlines. You guys are heroes."

5.3. pedagogy

Media role use and selection is the most relevant aspect in social,moral psychological and spiritual aspect.

5.4 Limitations/problems

To get the results of qualitative research is not enough to explain complex issues.

5.5 Recommendations

It is recommended that on social media the use of proper, nice and polished language is recommended. In modern time the language use on media response, has become the cause of psychological nuisance and disturbance. Enjoying the opportunity of living in net global community, the modern era man should open the generous hearts eyes as well to pray and thanks to creators blessings by ignoring fear, dissatisfaction, restlessness, greed, creed and materialistic approach aside. All religions, all elders should be respected as humanitarian grounds. Basic principles of humanitarianism rights from holy prophet's military approach should be honored, Mansoor. K (2018) highlighted that the holy prophet (P. B. U. H), during his 10-year-ruling in Median, had 85 battles. In all of these battles, the holy prophet ordered his soldiers and followers to respect humanitarianism rights on individual grounds. Life plans, schedules should be planned again according to latest scenario. As William Shakespeare has stipulated that the world is a stage and we are like characters to come on the stage, play our role that is fixed on the mind of people and fresh alive in the hearts and memories of people forever. As a film is recorded in camera role, similarly all deeds are recoded by divine power the creator.

In the film horror the stands as a warning to perform good deeds in life, they get reward in life and hereafter. Individual message on Facebook indicate to revise life priorities. What Sapp images shows to remember the creator to enjoy the bliss of life. The news clearly tells that simplicity in food saves life. Simplicity in residence saves time and mental burden, Simplicity of character traits is the crown of humanity. Simplicity in writing encourage literacy and learning.

Fig No.27 Conclusion.

(A s Broderick's M, 2002 research)

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APPENDICES**APPENDICES****PART-A****Teachers Data Collection 19****DATA COLLECTION ANALYSIS TEACHERS QUESTIONNAIRE**

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Culture is depicted through media				
2	during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home				
3	it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos				
4	Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal				
5	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator				
6	Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.				
7	COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.				
8	human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations				
9	Women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon				
10	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology				

B. 129 Students Data Collection

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Culture is depicted through media				
2	during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home				
3	it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos				
4	Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal				
5	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator				
6	Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.				
7	COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.				
8	human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations				
9	Women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon				
10	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology				

Results of the 129 students closed end Questionnaire %.

Sr No	Statement	Disagree(%)	Strongly disagree(%)	Agree(%)	Strongly Agree(%)
Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Culture is depicted through media	-	-	14	5
2	during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home	6	5	7	1
3	it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos	-	-	6	13
4	Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal	1	-	10	8
5	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator	-	-	4	15
6	Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.	2	2	13	2
7	COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.	-	-	9	10
8	human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations	5	4	9	1
9	Women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon	3	2	7	7
10	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology	3	-	8	8

Data Collection 19 Teachers**Data Collection 19 Teachers %**

Sr No	Statement	Disagree(%)	Strongly disagree(%)	Agree(%)	Strongly Agree(%)
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Data Collection 129 Students

Sr No	Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	Culture is depicted through media	4	6	68	51
2	during smart lockdown its pleasant feeling to have good chance to have happy time at home	62	33	17	17
3	it's better incorporated into everyday activities such as YouTube, Whats app, Instagram, Facebook, videos	2	5	43	79
4	Corona symptoms of hot Fever, pain in throat, continuous cough and breathing problems are to make strong believe with spiritual aspect that life is mortal	15	9	63	42
5	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology but give strength to hope in Creator	1	9	60	59
6	Ways to prevent the disease as washing hands, Cover Nose & Mouth When Sneezing, using Use Sanitizer and Avoiding Crowded Places (Social Distancing) are always good health measures.	13	7	90	19
7	COVID-19's impact has devastated individuals and families as well as the workforce, business, industries and the global economy as a whole. The marketing and technology industries in particular are currently reeling from the after-effects of the pandemic.	7	7	38	77
8	human rights are of great importance during lockdown situations	42	35	34	18
9	Women can help as integral part to balance economical disasture during lockdon	26	27	43	33
10	Isolation and quarantine prevent infection of coronavirus but damage the psychology	5	10	48	66

Data Collection 129 Students %**C**

1. How can you manage Impact of mass media and social media on psychological attitudes and behaviors towards the COVID-19 ?
2. What are the purposes of Behavior-change interventions to improve during COVID19 situations ?
3. How Can to get Through The Impact of Coronavirus on Pakistan Economy?
4. How should we improve the situation of psychological restlessness and mental anxiety in covid effects situations ?
5. How covid 19 is helpful in new revival of human mind, soul, psyche, behavior, atmosphere and surroundings ?

Q. No	Strongly disagree	disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Total
1	0	0	1	5	6
2	1	0	4	0	5
3	0	0	0	1	1
4	0	0	1	1	2
5	0	0	1	0	1

C TEACHER QUESTIONNAIRE

NAME OF TEACHER: _____ INSTITUTION: DPS & C G/sec, Fsd LEVEL OR GRADE: Secondary

Open ended question:

6. How can you manage Impact of mass media and social media on psychological attitudes and behaviors towards the COVID-19 ?

7. What are the purposes of Behavior-change interventions to improve during COVID19 situations ?

8. How Can to get Through The Impact of Coronavirus on Pakistan Economy?
Small businesses are particularly vulnerable

9. How should we improve the situation of psychological restlessness and mental anxiety in covid effects situations ?

5. How covid 19 is helpful in new revival of human mind, soul, psyche, behavior, atmosphere and surroundings ?

INFORMED CONSENT

The semio-semantic and social study of the Media Role in Relation with Covid -19 in Pakistan: A scientific and Spiritual Based Analysis

Ph.D English Researcher : Robina Shaukat

Phone: 03215674150

Email: robikaemail@gmail.com

Imperial College of Business Studies, ICBS Lahore.

Introduction

You are being invited to participate in a research study which aims to link. The study spans over two phases, phase 1 involves survey questionnaires to collect data and phase 2 involves interviews/discussions to collect data. This study is conducted as part of a PhD research project.

Confidentiality

Any information obtained during the research study will remain confidential and will be used for research purposes only. Your name or any type of identification will not be mentioned in any reports or publications that will be made based on findings of this study. Collected data will be analyzed in making general inferences [only] about the population under study. Every effort will be made by the researcher to preserve your confidentiality.

Participation

Your participation in this research study is voluntary. You may refuse to take part in the research or exit at any time you want. You are free to decline to answer any particular question on the survey form or during the interview that you do not wish to answer for any reason.

Declaration

Study is supervised by **Prof.Dr.Muhammad Shahbaz Arif** . I would like to assure you that this study has been reviewed and approved by the Advanced Studies and Research Board of Imperial University Lahore Pakistan.

Participant's Statement

I agree to participate in this PhD Study conducted by **Robina Shaukat** of the Humanities Department at Imperial University, Lahore Pakistan.

I have read and I understand the provided information and have had the opportunity to receive any additional details I wanted about the study. I also understand that this study has been reviewed and approved by the Advanced Studies and Research Board of Imperial University, Lahore Pakistan.

Thank You for your time and assistance in this **Study! Here is link for questionnaire please**

<https://forms.gle/6GzjiFLemyz7KwQWA>

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It's the grace of **ALMIGHTY ALLAH** that has led this work to its completion and who is the Most Gracious and All Compassionate. I can never dare to deny of His gifts that He has granted me, best of which is that He has provided me with the torch of eternal guidance in the form of His **Holy Prophet (PBUH)**, who is the knowledge for humanity as a whole.

I am highly obliged to **Dr Bashir Ahmad Samim**, Dr. Zulfiqar Ali, DR. Munnawar, Dr.Anees, **Sir.Usman**, Mr.Akhtar, Mr.Bilal, Mr. Sufyan, Mr.Faizan, Mr.Rana Rohail, Mr.Saad, for their sincere managerial and administrative supports.

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I would love to express my sincere thanks to my colleagues and friends who have always been a real source of motivation for me.

I am very thankful to my family. The prayers and support of my family has helped me throughout my work.

(Robina Shaukat)

Thesis Submission Approval Form**(Dr.Muhammad Shahbaz Arif)**

Thesis submitted by **ROBINA SHAUKAT**

Registration No **Student ID: LAENO13R16-009**

Discipline **REGULAR STUDENT**

Candidate for the degree of **PHD ENGLISH LINGUISTICS**

This thesis has been read by me and has been found to be satisfactory regarding content, English usage, format, citations, bibliographic style, and consistency, and thus fulfils the qualitative requirements of this study. It is ready for submission for internal and external evaluation.

Dr.Muhammad Shahbaz Arif

Ph.D England

Dean Department of English

Faculty of humanities and Social Sciences,

ICBS Lahore

Name of Supervisor

Signature of Supervisor

Date 29-12-2020.